

trans- Alkylations during Thermal Decarboxylation of 7:8-Dialkoxythioisocoumarin-3-Carboxylic Acids

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The decarboxylation of 7:8-dimethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid is attended with intermolecular *trans*-methylation yielding the methyl ester of the aforesaid acid—a result similar to that obtained in the related isocoumarin and isocarbostyryl derivatives. The dealkylated derivatives have also been isolated.

It has been shown earlier that the thermal decarboxylation of 7:8-dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid¹ and the related *iso*-carbostyryl² acid is not normal in as much as a mixture of products are obtained resulting from an intermolecular *trans*-alkylation involving the 8-alkoxyl group. The decarboxylation of 7:8-dimethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (I) studied earlier by Dijkman and Newbold³ was re-examined in light of the result obtained by us. This reaction in our hands gave a mixture of 7:8-dimethoxythioisocoumarin (II), a phenolic product, C₁₂H₁₀O₃S, m.p. 123-24° and a neutral compound C₁₃H₁₁O₃S, m.p. 152-53° (also isolated by Dijkman and Newbold). The phenolic compound showed the presence of a chelated carbonyl (1630 cm⁻¹ in KBr pellet) and identified as 7-methoxy-8-hydroxythioisocoumarin (III) and confirmed by (i) conversion into the known 7-methoxy-8-hydroxy-*iso*carbostyryl⁴ (VII) and (ii) by methylation to 7:8-dimethoxythioisocoumarin. The neutral compound mentioned above showed absorption at 1700 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl) and 1648 cm⁻¹ (thiolactone carbonyl⁵) and was equated with methyl 7:8-dimethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylate (IV) which was prepared for comparison.

7-Methoxy-8-ethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (V) was also prepared by standard route^{3,4} from 2-ethoxy-3-methoxy-6-aldehydobenzoic acid⁶ (VIII) (vide experimental). The decarboxylation of this acid afforded a mixture of products from which 7-methoxy-8-ethoxythioisocoumarin (VI) and 7-methoxy-8-hydroxythioisocoumarin were isolated amongst the identifiable compounds.

(I) R = Me, R' = COOH
(II) R = Me, R' = H

(VII)

1. J. N. Chatterjee, B. K. Banerjee and H. C. Jha, *Chem. Ber.*, 1965, **98**, 3279.

2. J. N. Chatterjee, H. C. Jha and B. K. Banerjee, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, **27**, 2281.

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3. G. T. Newbold and D. J. Dijkman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 1213.

* The C=O stretching frequency of thiolactone carbonyl of thioisocoumarin is found to be shifted to a lower frequency (1640-1650 cm⁻¹) in comparison with lactone carbonyl of isocoumarin (1740 cm⁻¹).

4. A. Kamal, A. Robertson and E. Tittensor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3375.

- (III) R = R' = H
 (IV) R = Me, R' = COOMe
 (V) R = Et, R' = COOH
 (VI) R = Et, R' = H

EXPERIMENTAL

(All m.ps. are uncorrected)

Decarboxylation of 7:8-dimethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid.—7:8-Dimethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid³ (1 g.) was mixed intimately with copper bronze (0.1 g.) and the mixture was heated in a metal bath at 270° till the evolution of carbon dioxide had visibly ceased. The product (0.7 g.), obtained on distillation in vacuum melted in a range. This product (0.6 g.) was taken in ether (50 c.c.) and washed thrice with small portions of sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water. The ether solution was extracted with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution (0.5%) (7 × 2 ml). The washings were mixed together and acidified by dropwise addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid. A yellow ppt. was obtained which was collected (80 mg.) and crystallised from ethanol in small deep yellow needles, m.p. 123-24°. The compound gave a deep green colouration with aqueous ferric chloride and was identified to be 7-methoxy-8-hydroxythioisocoumarin. Found: C, 57.20; H, 4.14. C₁₀H₈O₃S requires C, 57.69; H, 3.84%. *Infrared spectrum*—Chelated thiolactone carbonyl, absorption at 1640 cm⁻¹.

The ethereal layer was finally washed with water dried over MgSO₄ and the ether was removed furnishing an oily residue which soon solidified (0.62 g.). The product did not give any ferric reaction and still melted in a range. This was dissolved in alcohol (10 c.c.) and left to cool when pale yellow needles came as the first fraction in 1½ hour. This was collected (0.05 g.) and recrystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 152-153°. This product was identified as methyl 7:8-dimethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylate by mixed melting point determination (Newbold and Dijkman³ report m.p. 152°) and identity of the i.r. spectrum (ester carbonyl at 1700 cm⁻¹ and thiolactone carbonyl at 1648 cm⁻¹).

The filtrate was concentrated and left to cool when small yellow prismatic crystals were obtained which was recrystallised from petroleum-ether (00-80°), m.p. 92.94° (Dijkman and Newbold³ report m.p. 92-94°) (thiolactone carbonyl absorption at 1640 cm⁻¹).

Decarboxylation of 7-methoxy-8-hydroxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid: 7-Methoxy-8-hydroxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid was prepared following the method of Newbold and Dijkman³. The *methyl ester* prepared with ethereal diazomethane, crystallised from methanol in fine yellow needles, m.p. 169°. Found: C, 53.8; H, 4.1. C₁₂H₁₀O₃S requires: C, 54.1; H, 3.75%.

The acid (50 mg.) was mixed intimately with copper-bronze (7 mg.) and heated at 305-310° in a metal bath till the evolution of carbon dioxide had ceased. On distillation in vacuum a yellow oil was obtained which soon solidified. The product was taken in ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, and then with water and dried ($MgSO_4$). On removal of the solvent and crystallisation from alcohol 7-methoxy-8-hydroxythioisocoumarin was obtained in deep yellow prisms, m.p. 123-24°.

Methylation: The aforesaid hydroxythioisocoumarin (50 mg.) was taken with methyl iodide (1 c.c.) and freshly baked potassium carbonate (1 g.) in dry acetone (5 c.c.) and refluxed overnight. On working up in the usual manner the 7:8-dimethoxythioisocoumarin was obtained in quantitative yield.

Crystallisation with petroleum ether (60-80°) afforded needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 92-94°.

7:8-Dimethoxyisocarbostryl: 7:8-Dimethoxythioisocoumarin (0.15 g.) was taken with alcoholic ammonia (5 c.c., saturated at 0°) and left for 24 hours in a pressure bottle. The solution was filtered and the alcohol removed, when a light yellow gummy mass was obtained which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (60-80°) in small prisms, m.p. 178-79°. On admixture with the sample obtained from 7:8-dimethoxyisocoumarin² the m.p. remained undepressed. The i.r. spectra of the two were also identical.

The picrate was obtained in lemon yellow prisms from alcohol, m.p. and mixed m.p. 152°.

7-Methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostryl: 7-Methoxy-8-hydroxythioisocoumarin (25 mg.) was taken in alcoholic ammonia (3 ml., saturated at 0°) and left for 24 hours in a pressure bottle, the solution was filtered and on evaporation of the solvent the 7-methoxy-8-hydroxyisocarbostryl was obtained which was crystallised from benzene in small colourless needles, m.p. 210-11° identical with an authentic specimen.

The picrate obtained from alcohol in chocolate brown prisms melted at 195-96°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen.

7-Methoxy-8-ethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid. 2-Ethoxy-3-methoxy-6-aldehydrobenzoic acid (0.5 g.), was esterified with diazomethane and the ester was mixed with powdered rhodanine³ (0.3 g.) acetic acid (3 c.c.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.6 g.) and heated on a water bath for 45 minutes. The mixture was cooled, and triturated with water (25 ml) sodium hydroxide (4 g.) was added to it and heated on a water bath for one hour. The cooled solution was poured into dilute hydrochloric acid solution when alightly coloured crystalline precipitate (0.4 g.) of the 7-methoxy-8-ethoxy-thioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid was obtained, m.p. 248°. Found: C, 55.92; H, 4.56. $C_{13}H_{11}O_5S$ requires: C, 55.71; H, 4.28%.

The *methyl ester* prepared from ethereal diazomethane crystallised into yellow needles (methanol), m.p. 145-46°. Found: C, 57.32; H, 4.93. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5S$ requires: C, 57.15; H, 4.76%.

Decarboxylation of 7-methoxy-8-ethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid. 7-Methoxy-8-ethoxythioisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid (0.82 g.) was mixed intimately with copper bronze (30 mg.) and heated in a metal bath till complete evolution of carbon dioxide and then the product distilled in vacuum. The yellow distillate solidified readily (0.22 g.), gave a deep green ferric reaction and melted in a range. Thus the whole of the product was taken in ether (30 ml) and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the acid, if any. Then the ether solution was extracted with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution (1%) (6 × 2 ml). The combined alkaline extract was acidified with dropwise addition of conc. hydrochloric acid, when flocculent yellow precipitate was obtained which was collected (20 mg.) and crystallised from ethanol in slender prismatic needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-8-hydroxythioisocoumarin was 123-24°.

The ethereal layer was next washed with water and dried over $MgSO_4$. On removal of the ether a pale yellow residue was obtained which crystallised from petroleum ether in small light yellow needles, m.p. 97-98°. Found: C, 60.83; H, 5.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5S$ Requires: C, 61.02; H, 5.08%.

Infrared Spectrum.—Thiolactone carbonyl absorption at 1640 cm^{-1} .

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